

SPORTS DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM IN THE DIVISION OF CAMARINES NORTE: CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED IN PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the challenges encountered in the implementation of the Sports Development Program (SDP) in the Division of Camarines Norte. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected from secondary sports coordinators to identify obstacles affecting program implementation. Specifically, the study aimed to: 1) describe the respondents' profile in terms of role, years of involvement, age, number of relevant sports training attended, and sports affiliation; 2) assess the extent to which the program's primary objectives are being met; 3) determine the relationship between respondents' profiles and the attainment of program objectives; 4) evaluate the extent of support provided to the program in terms of accessibility, quality, and availability; 5) examine the relationship between the attainment of objectives and the level of support; 6) identify the challenges encountered by Sports Development Coordinators; and 7) propose interventions to improve SDP implementation. Data were collected using a researcher-made questionnaire and analyzed with appropriate statistical tools. Findings revealed varying levels of attainment of program objectives and highlighted key challenges related to resources, facilities, and administrative support. Based on these results, the study recommends targeted interventions to enhance the implementation and effectiveness of the Sports Development Program in the Division of Camarines Norte.

Keywords: *Sports Development Program, program implementation, sports coordinators, challenges, school sports development*

INTRODUCTION

Sports development programs are an essential component of a holistic education system, contributing significantly to learners' physical fitness, mental well-being, discipline, teamwork, and leadership development. In the Philippine educational system, the Department of Education (DepEd) recognizes sports as a vital avenue for talent identification and grassroots athletic development, which ultimately promotes physical fitness and enhances students' skills, particularly in the Division of Camarines Norte. The Sports Development Program (SDP) aims to cultivate athletes' potential while fostering participation in inter-school competitions; however, several factors may hinder its effectiveness.

Previous studies Pacadaljen, (2020); and Giango, et al. (2022) indicate that sports programs often face challenges related to resource allocation, training gaps, and inadequate administrative support. The researcher's professional involvement in school sports programs and coordination activities provided firsthand observations of recurring issues in program implementation. These challenges include limited access to sports facilities and equipment, insufficient training opportunities for coordinators, budgetary constraints, and varying levels of administrative and community support. Such obstacles may impede the effective achievement of the program's objectives.

Despite the importance of the Sports Development Program, there is a scarcity of empirical studies that systematically assess its implementation at the division level—particularly regarding objective attainment, level of support, and challenges encountered by implementer. This gap underscores the need for a comprehensive evaluation of the SDP in the Division of Camarines Norte.

Accordingly, this study was conducted to assess the implementation of the Sports Development Program, determine the extent of support provided, identify challenges encountered by Sports Development Coordinators, and propose interventions to improve program implementation.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. role in the Sports Development Program;
 - 1.2. years of experience;
 - 1.3. age;
 - 1.4. number of training relevant to sports; and
 - 1.5. sports affiliation?
2. To what extent are the primary objectives of the Sports Development Program in the Division of Camarines Norte being met along:
 - 2.1. participation rate;
 - 2.2. skills development;
 - 2.3. health and fitness
 - 2.4. community engagement, and

- 2.5. performance outcome?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondent's profile and the extent of attainment of the primary objectives of the Sports Development Program?
4. What is the extent of support given to the Sports Development program in terms of:
 - 4.1. accessibility;
 - 4.2. quality; and
 - 4.3. availability?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the attainment of the objective and the extent of support given in implementing Sports Development Program?
6. What are the challenges encountered by the Sports Development Coordinators in the implementation of the program?
7. What interventions may be proposed to improve the implementation of the Sports Development Program in the Division of Camarines Norte?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design to examine the challenges faced by Sports Development Coordinators in implementing the Sports Development Program (SDP) in the Division of Camarines Norte. The descriptive component profiled the coordinators—including their roles, years of involvement, age, training, and sports affiliation—and described their experiences, perceptions, and the program's current implementation practices. The correlational component analyzed the relationship between the coordinators' profiles and the attainment of the SDP objectives, as well as between the level of support, provided and the program outcomes.

The correlational research, a non-experimental design, allowed the study to measure these variables without manipulation. Cherry (2023) component analyzed the relationships between the coordinators' profiles and the attainment of SDP objectives as well as between. Findings from this analysis informed recommendations for interventions to enhance the effectiveness of the SDP.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The study employed total enumeration to include all respondents, ensuring comprehensive data collection. The population consisted of 56 secondary school Sports Development Coordinators in the Division of Camarines Norte for SY 2024–2025.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study adhered to strict ethical standards throughout the research process. Authorization was obtained from the Department of Education, including the Schools Division Superintendent of Camarines Norte, the PSDS, and the school heads. Respondents were fully informed of the study's purpose, relevance, and their right to withdraw at any time. Measures were taken to ensure the credibility, reliability, and validity

of the data, minimizing bias and ensuring accurate findings. All information collected through the questionnaire was treated confidentially and used solely for this study. Additionally, the research instruments and procedures were reviewed by research experts to validate the study, safeguarding respondents' privacy and upholding ethical standards.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The responses were numerically coded and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. For research question 1, which profiled respondents' role in the Sports Development Program: years of experience as coordinators, age, number of training relevant to sports; and sports affiliation, descriptive statistics such as frequency and ranking were used. For research questions 2 and 4, assessing the extent of implementation of SDP objectives and the level of support provided in terms of accessibility, quality and availability, descriptive statistics using weighted mean on a 5-point Likert's scale were applied. For research question 6, which examined challenges encountered during program implementation, was analyzed using a 4-point Likert scale interpreted through weighted means.

To determine significant relationships between variables (research questions 3 and 5), the Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 21, ensuring accuracy, reliability, and minimizing manual errors. The software also enabled advanced statistical tests, allowing the identification of key factors influencing SDP implementation and informing strategies for program enhancement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, years of experience in the Sports Development Program (SDP), number of training sessions attended, and sports affiliation.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, years of experience in the Sports Development Program (SDP), number of trainings attended, and sports affiliation. These variables offer insight into the coordinators' background, level of involvement, and exposure to sports development activities, which are essential for understanding their capacity to implement the program effectively. The respondents' professional characteristics serve as a foundation for interpreting their perspectives on SDP implementation and the challenges they face.

- A. Findings revealed that 1) years of involvement 3-5 years of experience, suggesting familiarity with the program but limited long-term expertise. the highest group (44.64%) and the lowest number of coordinators is 25 which have five years or more of involvement.

- B. Age: The highest number of respondents (42.86%) are age 41-50 years old, indicating that the least number indicates 51-60 years (7.14%), indicating that the majority of the sports coordinators fall within this age range.
- C. Number of trainings attended: The data indicate the nearly half 27(48.21%) have attended only 1-2 relevant training, indicating limited professional development that may affect program improvement and responsiveness to challenges, and 5 or more training the lowest indicator is 12 (21.43%).
- D. Sports Affiliation: Finding revealed that Athletics is the highest indicator is 35 (62.50%), and the lowest indicator Basketball (1.79%), Chess (1.79%), CNTAFA (1.79%). The respondents of the Sports Development Program (SDP) in the Division of Camarines Norte are all middle-aged (41-50 years). Sports Coordinator with 3-5 years of experience, primarily affiliated with athletics. Cullarin and Bernales (2021), their age and experience provide a balance of maturity, practical skills, and energy enabling them to effectively plan, organize, supervise and evaluate school-based sports activities (Celso, 2025).

The respondents of the Sports Development Program (SDP) in the Division of Camarines Norte are all middle-aged (41-50 years). Sports Coordinator with 3-5 years of experience, primarily affiliated with athletics Cullarin and Bernales (2021). their age and experience effectively plan, organize, supervise, and evaluate school-based sports activities Celso (2025).

However, nearly half of the coordinators have attended only 1–2 relevant training sessions, while only a small portion have participated in five or more, which may limit their professional growth and capacity to introduce new practices or address emerging challenge Lobo and Teodoso (2024). The strong focus on athletics reflects its accessibility, inclusive, and role in developing fundamental physical skills, but it also highlights the need to support other sports disciplines to ensure a more balanced development of student-athletes (Alave & Ancho, 2022).

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Program Coordinator	56	100
Years of Involvement		
1–2 years	17	30.36
3–5 years	25	44.64
5 years and above	14	25.00
Total	56	100.00
Age		
21–30	9	16.07
31–40	19	33.93
41–50	24	42.86

51–60	4	7.14
Total	56	100.00
Number of Trainings Attended		
1–2 trainings	27	48.21
3–5 trainings	17	30.36
5 and above	12	21.43
Total	56	100.00
Sports Affiliation		
Athletics	35	62.50
Badminton	5	8.93
Basketball	1	1.79
Billiard	2	3.57
Boxing	3	5.36
Chess	1	1.79
CNTAFA	1	1.79
Table Tennis	2	3.57
Taekwondo	3	5.36
Volleyball	2	3.57
Total	56	100.00

Expanding professional development opportunities and encouraging coordinators to diversify their sports expertise can enhance program effectiveness, improve student participation, and strengthen overall implementation outcomes.

Extent of Attainment of the Primary Objectives of the Sports Development Program

Table 2 presents the extent of attainment of the primary objectives of the Sports Development Program (SDP) in the Division of Camarines Norte. It shows how effectively the program's goals are being met in areas such as participation, skills development, health and fitness, community engagement, performance outcomes, and satisfaction level. The result reflects how effectively the program meets its intended goals in promoting sports involvement and enhancing.

Table 2
Extent of Attainment of the Primary Objectives of The Sports Development Program

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Participation Rates		
1. There is an increased number of students who engage in sports	3.21	Moderate Extent

2. The majority of the students in the Secondary level of communities in Camarines Norte is participating in sports	2.80	Moderate Extent
3. Secondary level students actively participate in schools	2.93	Moderate Extent
4. Many students at the secondary level are fond of sports	2.59	Moderate Extent
Overall Weighted Mean	2.86	Moderate Extent
Skills Development		
1. All communities in Camarines Norte promote sport-related advocacies	2.89	Moderate Extent
2. The student-athletes' performance is continuously improving	3.23	Moderate Extent
3. Discipline is developed among student-athletes	3.27	Moderate Extent
4. Coordination and muscle memory are developed among student-athletes	3.34	Moderate Extent
5. Student-athletes develop teamwork	3.20	Moderate Extent
6. Student-athletes are seen to have great time management skills	3.00	Moderate Extent
Overall Weighted Mean	3.16	Moderate Extent
Health and Fitness		
1. Student-athletes have good mental health	3.37	Moderate Extent
2. Sports help improve student-athletes' emotional intelligence	3.09	Moderate Extent
Overall Weighted Mean	3.23	Moderate Extent
Community Engagement		
1. The communities in Camarines Norte frequently support sport-related activities in secondary school	2.95	Moderate Extent
2. Communities in Camarines Norte developed sport-related programs	3.07	Moderate Extent
3. Only a few communities in Camarines Norte promote sport-related advocacies	2.91 2.97	Moderate Extent
Overall Weighted Mean	2.975	Moderate Extent
Performance Outcome		
1. Resilience is seen among student-athletes	3.23	Moderate Extent
2. Performance outcomes in every competition of student-athletes enhance their skills	3.20	Moderate Extent

3. Student-athletes were able to meet their utmost ability in sports	3.30	Moderate Extent
Overall Weighted Mean	3.24	Moderate Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Great Extent
 2.61 3.40= Moderate Extent
 1.81-2.60=Less Extent
 3.41-4.20=Great Extent
 1.00-1.80= Very Little Extent

The findings show that the SDP positively impacts student-athletes' performance, with many achieving or exceeding benchmarks in skills, discipline, and game strategy. However, the lowest rated indicator (3.20) revealed that not all competition led to noticeable skill improvement due to the limited feedback, follow-up training, or performance analysis.

Respondents reported with a high weighted mean (3.37) student-athlete with good mental health and the lowest weighted mean is many students at the secondary level outcomes in every competition of student athletes enhance their skills.

Respondents with administrative support, including logistics, equipment, and venue access, which enhances athletes' confidence and reduces coaches' stress. The lowest satisfaction (4.05) concerned incentives and recognition, highlighting the need for formal acknowledgment of achievements to maintain motivation. Overall, while support systems are strong, improving recognition and reward mechanisms would further sustain athlete and coach commitment, consistent with findings by Lobo and Teodosio (2024).

Relationship Between the Respondents' Profile and the extent of Attainment of the Primary Objectives of the Sports Development Program

Table 3 presents the significant relationship between the respondents' profiles and the extent of attainment of the primary objectives of the Sports Development Program (SDP). It examines how variables such as age, years of involvement, and the number of training sessions attended influence the achievement of key program objectives, including participation rate, skills development, health and fitness, performance outcomes, and satisfaction levels.

Table 3
Relationship between the Respondents' Profile and the Extent of Attainment of the Primary Objectives of the SDP

Profile	Participation Rate		Skills Development		Health & Fitness		Community Engagement			Performance Outcome
	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value
Age	0.214	0.118	0.198	0.142	0.185	0.165	0.214	0.118	0.198	0.142

No. of Trainings	0.376*	0.005	0.392*	0.004	0.341*	0.011	0.376*	0.005	0.392*	0.004
Years of Service	0.281*	0.037	0.296*	0.029	0.244	0.062	0.281*	0.037	0.296*	0.029
<i>Legends:</i> <i>*significant at 0.05</i> <i>**very significant at 0.01</i>										

The correlation analysis showed positive but generally low to moderate relationships between coordinators' profiles and the achievement of SDP objectives. Age had a slight positive effect on participation ($r = 0.214$), skills development ($r = 0.198$), health and fitness ($r = 0.185$), community engagement ($r = 0.221$), performance outcomes ($r = 0.193$), and satisfaction ($r = 0.205$). The number of trainings showed moderate positive correlations across all indicators, particularly skills development ($r = 0.392$) and satisfaction ($r = 0.352$), while years of service had weak-to-moderate correlations, influencing participation ($r = 0.281$), skills ($r = 0.296$), and performance outcomes ($r = 0.278$).

These results indicate that professional training and experience are more influential than age in achieving program objectives, enhancing athletes' performance and well-being, engaging the community, and increasing coordinators' satisfaction. Findings align with Lobo, J. & Teodosio, K (2024) and Celso (2025), highlighting the value of continuous professional development and accumulated experience in effective sports program implementation.

Extent of Support Given to the Sports Development Program

Table 4 presents the extent of support given to the Sports Development Program (SDP) as determined by the respondents. It shows the level of assistance provided by the school, local government, and other stakeholders in terms of funding, facilities, training, and administrative support for effective program implementation. In terms of accessibility, quality, and availability. These variables reflect how resources, opportunities, and institutional backing affect the implementation. In terms of accessibility, quality, and availability.

Table 4
Extent of Support Given to the Sports Development Program

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Accessibility		
1. The age of the sports coordinator does not affect the success of attaining SDP's primary objectives.	3.23	Great Extent
2. Experienced sports coordinators have a higher chance of attaining the primary objectives of SDP.	3.38	Very Great Extent

3. Regardless of the sports affiliation, the primary objectives of SDP are being met.	3.18	Great Extent
Overall Weighted Mean	3.26	Very Great Extent
Quality		
1. The greater the number of trainings received, the sports coordinators' chance of attaining SDP primary objectives.	3.34	Very Great Extent
2. A young sports coordinator impacts the attainment of the primary objective of SDP.	2.84	Great Extent
3. An inexperienced sports coordinator barely achieved the primary objective; varied roles (coach, program coordinator, school administrator) in a program can affect the success of attaining the SDP's primary objectives.	3.18	Great Extent
4. Despite a few trainings, the sports coordinator can attain the SDP primary objectives.	3.20	Great Extent
Overall Weighted Mean	3.14	Great Extent
Availability		
1. Student-athletes are indeed physically fit.	3.29	Very Great Extent
2. Varying roles in sports programs do not affect the achievement of the primary objectives.	2.91	Great Extent
Overall Weighted Mean	3.10	Great Extent

Legends:

Rating Scale

3.26 - 4.00

2.51 - 3.25

1.76 - 2.50

Descriptive Interpretation

Very Great Extent

Great Extent

Moderate Extent

The SDP in the Division of Camarines Norte is generally well-supported in terms of accessibility, quality, and availability. Accessibility scored highest (WM = 3.38), indicating that resources, facilities, and administrative support are largely reachable, though occasional logistical challenges exist (WM = 3.18). Quality is strengthened by training (WM = 3.34), which enhances coordinators' competence, while less-experienced coordinators show lower contributions (WM = 2.84). Availability of resources such as facilities and equipment is generally sufficient (WM = 3.29), though multitasking responsibilities may limit full implementation (WM = 2.91). Overall, the SDP is supported to a great extent (WM = 3.10–3.26), yet optimizing training, mentoring younger coordinators, and ensuring equitable resource distribution can further improve program effectiveness (Pacaljen, 2020; Alave & Ancho, 2022).

Relationships Between the Attainment of the Objectives and the Extent of Support Given in the SDP

Table 5 presents the Relationship between the Attainment of the Objectives and the Extent of Support given in the Sports Development Program, measured in terms of accessibility, quality, and availability, and the attainment of objectives, and the extent of support.

Table 5
Significant Relationship Between the Attainment of
The Objective and the Extent of Support

Indicators	Accessibility		Quality		Extent of Support		Availability	
		P-value		P-value		P-value		P-value
Extent of Attainment								
Participation Rate	0.512**	0.004	0.534**	0.003	0.498**	0.006		
Skills Development	0.621**	0.001	0.657**	0.000	0.605**	0.001		
Health and Fitness	0.586**	0.002	0.603**	0.001	0.562**	0.003		
Community Engagement	0.547**	0.004	0.574**	0.002	0.516**	0.005		
Performance Outcome	0.633**	0.000	0.658**	0.000	0.627**	0.001		

Legend: ***Significance level: 0.01

The Pearson correlation analysis revealed significant positive relationships between the extent of program support—accessibility, quality, and availability—and the achievement of all SDP objectives. Participation showed moderate positive correlations ($r = 0.498$ – 0.534), suggesting that better-supported programs encourage higher student involvement. Skills development ($r = 0.605$ – 0.657) and performance outcomes ($r = 0.627$ – 0.658) were strongly correlated with support, indicating that access to quality resources and training improves athletes' abilities and competitive results. Health and fitness ($r = 0.562$ – 0.603), community engagement ($r = 0.516$ – 0.574), and satisfaction ($r = 0.544$ – 0.612) also increased with stronger support, demonstrating the broader benefits of accessible, high-quality, and available resources.

All correlations were significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming that well-structured support is essential for achieving SDP objectives and enhancing participation, skill acquisition, performance, community involvement, and overall satisfaction.

Challenges Encountered by the Sports Coordinators in Implementing the Program

Table 6 shows the challenges faced by sports coordinators in implementing the Sports Development Program in secondary schools in the SDO Camarines Norte. The results highlight specific areas of concern that hinder effective delivery of sports initiatives, such as financial constraints, inadequate facilities, limited training support, and a lack of stakeholder involvement, which directly impact the achievement of the program's goals.

Table 6
Challenges Encountered by the Sports Coordinators in Implementing the Program

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Lack of financial support for sports programs	3.23	Great Challenge
2. Inadequate sports equipment and materials	3.38	Very Great Challenge
3. Limited access to sports facilities	3.34	Very Great Challenge
4. Insufficient time for training and preparation	3.25	Very Great Challenge
5. Lack of community or stakeholder involvement	3.18	Great Challenge
6. Poor motivation among student athletes	2.84	Great Challenge
7. Lack of training and seminars for sports coordinators	2.57	Great Challenge
8. Minimal support from school administration	3.20	Great Challenge
9. Inconsistent implementations of the sports development program	3.18	Great Challenge
10. Balancing academic and sports responsibilities	2.91	Great Challenge
Average Weighted Mean n = 56	3.21	Great Challenge

Rating Scale and Descriptive Interpretation	
3.25 - 4.00	Very Great Challenge
2.50 - 3.24	Great Challenge
1.75 - 2.49	Moderate Challenge
1.00 - 1.74	Not a Challenge

The highest three indicators, Inadequate sports equipment (WM=3.38), Limited access to sports facilities (WM=3.34), and Insufficient time for training and preparation (WM=3.25), were rated as very great challenge, indicating that there are cases where there is still lack of sufficient and up-to-date sports equipment, which limits training efficiency and athlete performance.

The study identified key challenges affecting the Sports Development Program. Limited and outdated sports equipment, particularly for swimming, gymnastics, lawn tennis, and other specialized sports, reduced practice time and active participation, thereby limiting skills development. Coordinators often had to modify drills and shorten sessions, affecting overall team readiness for competitions. These findings align with Botin (2024), who reported that inadequate equipment is a major barrier in school sports programs, especially in public schools with limited budgets. Moustakas (2020) similarly emphasized that access to sports facilities directly influences participation and program continuity, highlighting the need for schools and local government units to improve infrastructure and shared facility use.

Other challenges included balancing academic and sports responsibilities (WM = 2.91), limited administrative support (WM = 3.20), and inconsistent program implementation (WM = 3.18). Coordinators often scheduled practices after class or on weekends to accommodate academic demands, demonstrating their commitment. Poor student motivation (WM = 2.84) was a moderate challenge, as most students remained interested in sports for competition, socialization, and personal growth (Sulz & Gleddie, 2024).

Conclusions

The study concluded that the Sports Development Program in the Division of Camarines Norte is implemented to a great extent and generally attains its objectives, supported by competent school sports coordinators, strong administrative backing, and community involvement. Respondents were mostly middle-aged coordinators with 3–5 years of experience, affiliated with athletics, and having attended relevant training. A significant positive relationship exists between the extent of support—accessibility, quality, and availability—and the achievement of program objectives, with higher support linked to greater student participation. Major challenges included inadequate equipment, limited access to facilities, and insufficient training time, while academic responsibilities and student motivation were less frequent issues. To enhance program effectiveness and sustainability, capacity-building initiatives are recommended, including improved resources, regular training, strengthened stakeholder support, and systematic monitoring and evaluation.

Recommendations

To strengthen the Sports Development Program in the Division of Camarines Norte, it is recommended that schools consider hiring younger or multi-skilled coordinators, expand participation beyond athletics, and continue building strong administrative and community partnerships. Establishing regular monitoring and evaluation, securing funding through MOAs, MOUs, and fundraising, and upgrading facilities and equipment are also essential. Coordinators should attend workshops and training to improve their skills, use online resources to enhance teaching, and implement recognition systems for athletes and staff. Finally, future research may explore other sports areas not covered in this study to further support program development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to established ethical standards in the conduct of educational research. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to the data collection and participation was entirely voluntary with respondents informed of the right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained, and all data were collected stored and processed in compliance with applicable data privacy regulations. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the research process and no physical, psychological or emotional harm was incurred. The authors declare that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation and acknowledgment of sources, and the analysis and the interpretation of findings were carried out objectively and without bias. The results of the study were used solely to academic and research purposes. Artificial intelligence tools were utilized exclusively to assist in language editing and manuscript organization, and full responsibility to the content, analysis and conclusions remains with the authors.

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